

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE INTESTINAL MICROBIOME AND THE KETOGENIC DIET IN PEOPLE WITH AUTISTIC SPECTRUM DISORDERS

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Abstract

Background. The pathogenesis of autism spectrum disorder is not fully understood, but involves a combination of genetic, environmental, and immune dysfunction factors. The gut-brain axis is viewed as a communication pathway between the gut and the brain and is a two-way communication system. A growing body of evidence suggests that the gut-brain axis participates in the pathogenesis of autism spectrum disorder.

Objective. To evaluate diet as a therapeutic approach to ameliorate symptoms of autism spectrum disorder, review the evidence for the use of metabolic therapies such as the low-carbohydrate ketogenic diet in the treatment of autism spectrum disorder.

Materials and methods. Autism spectrum disorder is associated with several comorbidities, including gastrointestinal disorders, feeding problems, picky eating, and obesity. The implementation of a nutritional program with the ketogenic diet can have very good results in improving symptoms in autism.

Results. The severity of symptoms in autism is influenced by the appearance of imbalances in the intestinal microbiome and the application of a ketogenic diet can have the effect of reducing them.

Conclusion. The ketogenic diet could be useful for children with ASD but it is difficult to achieve because they have a selective diet eating only certain foods sometimes for a long time which can be a major impediment.

Keywords: autism spectrum disorder, ketogenic diet, microbiome, carbohydrates.

The human microbiome is now even considered to be our “last organ” (Baquero *et al.*, 2012). Research on the human microbiome has advanced from a fledgling field to a flourishing area of medical research with more than US\$1.7 billion being spent only over the past decade alone (Proctor *et al.*, 2019).

In 1988, Whipps and colleagues working on the ecology of rhizosphere microorganisms provided the first definition of the term microbiome (Whipps *et al.*, 1988). They described the “microbiome” as a combination of the words “micro” and “biome”, naming a “characteristic microbial community” in a “reasonably well-defined habitat which has distinct physio-chemical properties” as their “theatre of activity”. This definition represents a substantial advancement of the definition of a microbial community, as it defines a microbial community with distinct properties and functions and its interactions with its environment, resulting in the formation of specific ecological niches. However, there are many other microbiome definitions that have been published in the last few decades. The currently most cited definition by Lederberg (Lederberg *et al.*, 2001). Describes microbiomes within an ecological context, as a community of commensal, symbiotic, and pathogenic microorganisms within a body space or other environment. Marchesi and Ravel focused in their definition on the genomes and microbial (and viral) gene expression patterns and proteomes in a given environment and its prevailing biotic and abiotic conditions (Marchesi *et al.*, 2015).

All these definitions imply that general concepts of macro-ecology could be easily applied to microbe-microbe as well as to microbe-host interactions.

Microbiomes are a complex and dynamic network of microorganisms (bacteria, viruses, fungi, archaea) that adapt and live in a functional relationship with their specific habitats (e.g. human, soil, plant, water, animals, production sites along the food chain) (6Berg *et al.*, 2020). Neighbouring microbiome ecosystems exert mutual influences, even when physically separated (e.g. animal and soil) (Flandroy *et al.*, 2018). In addition, microbiomes are very sensitive to environmental conditions and exposure to substances of different nature. In humans, various factors (e.g. genetics, diet, drugs, lifestyle, oxygen, pH) contribute to shaping the microbiomes’ subpopulations along the various sections of the gastrointestinal tract (Shetty *et al.*, 2017).

Since the microbiome may play a role in human homeostasis, it can be used as a target for different dietary interventions to maintain and promote health (e.g. optimizing fibre intake, administration of pre- and probiotics) (Wilson *et al.*, 2020). On the other hand, microbiome disruptors (e.g. imbalanced diet) are also attracting attention as they may lead to dysbiosis, which can eventually result in adverse effects on human health (Das and Nair, 2019). Much of the current interest gathers around the capacity of food additives, chemical residues (pesticides and veterinary drugs), antibiotics or other environmental pollutants to lead to biologically

relevant microbiome perturbations (Cao *et al.*, 2020; Chiu *et al.*, 2020).

The definition, which contains all important points that are valid even 30 years after its publication in 1988, was extended by two explanatory sentences differentiating the terms microbiome and microbiota and pronouncing its dynamic character. The microbiome is defined as a characteristic microbial community occupying a reasonable well-defined habitat which has distinct physio-chemical properties. The microbiome not only refers to the microorganisms involved but also encompasses their theatre of activity, which results in the formation of specific ecological niches. Autism spectrum disorder affects approximately 1% of children worldwide, is predominantly male, and varies in severity. The term "spectrum" refers to the range of symptoms and levels of impairment that individuals with autism spectrum disorder may experience. Autism spectrum disorder is characterized by deficits in sociality and communication and increased repetitive and/or restrictive behaviors (Cheng *et al.*, 2017; Alam *et al.*, 2023).

The ketogenic diet, a high fat, adequate protein, low carbohydrate diet, has, during the past decade, had a resurgence of interest for the treatment of difficult-to-control seizures in children. This review traces its history, reviews its uses and side effects, and discusses possible alternatives and the diet's possible mechanisms of action. Finally, this review looks toward possible future uses of the ketogenic diet for conditions other than epilepsy. In medicine, it is mainly used to treat severe epileptic seizures in children. The diet causes the body to primarily burn fat for energy and consume fewer carbohydrates. Carbohydrates in food are normally converted into glucose, which is then released into the blood throughout the body, which is especially important for use as fuel for the brain. However, if the diet contains very few carbohydrates, the liver will convert the fat into fatty acids and ketone bodies. Ketone bodies are transported through the blood and replace glucose as an energy source. The increase of ketone bodies in the blood is a physiological state called ketosis, which leads to amelioration of epileptic seizures and a reduction in their frequency (Freeman *et al.*, 2007).

The results of a meta-analysis show that eating behavior is 4 times more difficult in children with autism, they are inattentive, anxious or agitated during meals, and have extreme food selectivity (with preferences for certain colors, textures) and food rituals (Wiliam și colab., 2013).

CASE STUDY

M. E. – boy, born in Constanta on May 19, 2005, premature, at 26 weeks.

The diagnosis: 1. Infantile autism 2. Retinopathy of prematurity

Personal medical history:

Before his birth my mother lost two pregnancies, one at four and a half months and one at five and a half months due to marital stress. He had surgery for retinopathy of prematurity in Belgium at the age of five months and has been wearing contact lenses since the age of nine months. At the age of two and a half, he was

admitted to Professor Doctor Alexandru Obregia Hospital where he was diagnosed with autism.

Somatic, stature and thoracic development within normal limits: attractive appearance, proportional body.

She is the second child of the family, the first child being a girl, born in 2000, who is now a psychology student in Bucharest. At the birth of M.E. the mother was 35 years old and the father 38 years old. Mother was a housewife, father was an agricultural engineer. There were frequent quarrels in the family, the father having an extramarital affair. They have been separated since 2013. He attended preschool courses at the age of four at the Cristina center, at the age of five at the Orizont Center. He was educated at the age of seven at School number 1-Delfinul, for children with special needs, where he is currently enrolled and home-schooled.

Neurological examination: EEG with diffuse bioelectric abnormalities without detectable brain lesions.

Recommendations:

- He has been receiving neurological treatment since he was one year old, currently taking the following medication: Leveritacetam and Lamotrix.

- The establishment of a recuperative educational program, including psychological stimulation and speech therapy.

Brief description of the manifestation of autistic syndrome:

It is characterized by strong emotional disturbances, it is attached to the mother. He has angry reactions directed at things, people and himself. This indicates opposition, neurovegetative lability, in which excitation predominates, poor attention, poor concentration and big problems with sleep. He is not interested in toys that embody people or animals. Handle objects with ease.

He has problems with constipation, the agitation being much greater during this period.

In January 2023, he did several medical investigations, including microbiome analysis. He has enterotype 1 with a large number of Bacteroides, Clostridium, Enterobacter spp., Escherichia spp., Klebsiella spp. and Serratia spp.. He contacted a nutritionist doctor who recommended him to follow a ketogenic diet. Followed the program for 1 month. After that, the symptoms improved a lot, which helps him to have better results at school.

CONCLUSIONS

In the case of our case study, imbalances in the intestinal microbiome may be the cause of worsening symptoms in autism. A balance at the digestive level can be the secret to establishing a state of homeostasis.

A low-carb ketogenic diet is, in our case, an effective treatment for ameliorating the symptoms of autism spectrum disorders.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that the study was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be interpreted as a potential conflict of interest.

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